

SROC Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

November, 05-06 2022
Ethno Complex Vrđnickska kula, Vrđnik

CBCT imaging dose-quality measurements in pelvis cancer radiotherapy treatments

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Introduction

Nowadays, the cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) imaging is an inseparable part of modern radiotherapy treatments. The aim of this study was to investigate absorbed dose – image quality dependence for pelvis cancer radiotherapy treatments of two different type of linear accelerator machines at Oncology Institute of Vojvodina.

Materials and methods

The absorbed dose and image quality of pelvis CBCT imaging protocols were performed at Elekta Versa HD (with four protocols) and Varian TrueBeam (with two protocols) linear accelerators. CBCT imaging protocols were investigated in following manner: the point absorbed dose was measured by Semiflex ionization chamber in target center and all organs at risk in anthropomorphic IMRT Pelvis phantom; standard image quality parameters were measured with Catphan phantom and analyzed by Smári image analysis service.

Results

The absorbed doses at Elekta Versa HD machine were in the range from 10 mGy to 63 mGy. The doses from Prostate CBCT imaging protocol were 1.4 times higher than doses from Pelvis CBCT imaging protocol. The absorbed doses at Varian TrueBeam machine were in the range from 24 mGy to 99 mGy. The doses from Pelvis CBCT imaging protocol were 2.2 times higher than doses from Large Pelvis CBCT imaging protocol. The image quality show no significant differences between same imaging system.

Conclusion

Based on the results of absorbed dose to point and image quality correlation, CBCT imaging protocol with lower doses is recommended. It should be borne in mind that any radiation exposure must be justified.

Keywords: CBCT imaging, pelvis radiotherapy, imaging dose, image quality

**SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress
2022**

Urednik
Olivera Ivanov

Izdavač
Institut za Onkologiju Vojvodine

Grafička priprema i štampa
NS digiprint, Novi Sad

Tiraž
200

ISBN 978-86-82113-15-7

CIP – Каталогizacija u publikaciji
Biblioteka Mатице српске, Нови Сад

616-006(048.3)

SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress (2022 ; Vrdnik)

Abstract book / Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress,
November, 05-06 2022 Ethno Complex Vrdnicka kula,
Vrdnik ; [urednik Olivera Ivanov]. - Novi Sad : Institut za
Onkologiju Vojvodine, 2022 (Novi Sad : NS digiprint).
– 56 str. : ilustr. ; 21 cm

Tiraž 200.

ISBN 978-86-82113-15-7

a) Онкологија – Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 78911241